

Patterns of Social and Economic Development in Hisar District Haryana

Naveen Nalwa
Research Scholar
Department of Geography
Om Sterling Global University, Hisar.

Abstract:- Hisar is one of India's minority-concentrated districts that lags behind in terms of socioeconomic indicators (Category B1). To build a multi sectoral development plan with the most recent gaps and priorities, a baseline study was undertaken. Because the researcher is from District Hisar, he did this study on his own time. The study's major purpose is to look at the social and economic growth of Hisar, Haryana.

Keywords:- Social development, Economic development, Hisar District, multisectoral development plan.

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of social development is to improve the social and economic well-being of societies or social groupings, which are always made up of unique individuals. Social development is related with self-development since it is considered as the growth of the individual human being. It represents the community's overall economic and social well-being progress. A country's growth requires social development. It examines social indicators such as age structure, age groupings, sex ratio, literacy, women's empowerment, occupational structure, and other social indicators.

The concept of development can be contrasted with the concept of people's quality of life and social well-being, which considers not only the social issue, but also other intangible aspects of social human life such as safety, quality of life, health, physical health, decision-making, demography, cultural aspects, environmental quality, and social-life, among others. When a social issue impacts society as a whole in some manner, it becomes a social problem. A personal issue is not the same as a societal one. Someone's social issues may be very personal to them. Crime, gender inequality, and other social issues such as poverty, health, social inequality, injustice, social insecurity, unemployment, human rights, and freedom are some of the important social issues.

II. STUDY AREA

Hisar is one of Haryana's most significant and rapidly rising urban centers, situated at 29°09' North latitude and 75°42' East longitude. Hisar has become an important part of Haryana's metropolitan landscape. It has risen as a result of its geographical position. Its position is such that any construction must be done away from the main highway and railway line. Faridbad, Gurgaon, and Rohtak have diverse causes for their development, however Hisar's rise is solely based on its potential for expansion and its location in the area.

Fig.1: Map of hisar district

A. Objectives

The following goals were developed based on the literature study.

- Examine the district's social and economic progress.
- To establish a multi-sectoral development plan that incorporates the most recent deficiencies and priorities.
- To explore the Hisar district's literacy rate's evolution.
- To examine the social, economic, health, and infrastructure aspects of the Hisar district's people.

B. Review Of Literature

Veer Sain (2014) performed a research in Hisar district, Haryana's Hansi and Barwala Blocks, which were chosen for their large area and productivity under guava cultivation. In addition, the Hisar market was chosen for the market research. Finally, for this research, 20 growers were chosen at random from two blocks in the Hisar area. Marketing margins, marketing price spread, and marketing efficiency were estimated using a budgeting approach and different economic instruments based on the type of the data. The setup cost in Hisar district was Rs.38040, which was attributable to superior orchard management; the main item of expenditure was the cost of irrigation, which was calculated. The expense of running a guava orchard grew from the first to the seventh year. Plant protection, manures, and fertilizers were determined to have the highest operating costs per hectare per year from the first to seventh years. The intercropping net returns varied from Rs. 36670 per hectare in the first year to Rs. 22560 per hectare in the fifth year of the orchard.

Manoj Kumar (2016) attempted to comprehend educational progress, age and sex patterns, occupational and economic structure at the family level in Gujjaran Mohalla, a caste-based segregated mohalla inhabited by Gujjar caste, and one of the oldest mohallas in Hisar city. The current project makes use of many types of data and maps gathered from a variety of sources, both public and unpublished. Secondary data is acquired from books, historical documents, Google Earth images, and other sources. The basic data came from a census household survey conducted in the Gujjaran Mohalla in October of 2014. The socio-economic survey of 47 homes was conducted via the use of structured questions. The location, cultural environment, and land usage have all been shown on maps. The literacy rate was calculated without taking into account the population of children aged 0 to 6. Additionally, the number of literate people is split into preprimary, primary, middle, matric, senior secondary, and higher education. The gender discrepancy in literacy level was assessed using Sopher's disparity index, which was modified by Kundu and Rao (1985). In this research, both major and marginal employees are included in the workforce. Gujjars have a high level of social development but a moderate to poor level of economic development. Despite substantial vocational diversity, they have shown a relatively low degree of social engagement with other castes in society.

In her research, **Rachna Singh (2021)** discovers that among the many types of animal husbandry, dairying is regarded as a "treasure" of the Indian rural economy. In developing nations like India, the profile of dairy farmers is

an essential aspect in the design and execution of assistance programs to encourage dairy farming for rural development and the adoption of modern dairy technology. The research was carried out in the Haryana district of Hisar, taking this into account. 73.3 percent of the 60 dairy producers polled were middle-aged, with an average age of 43 years. With a mean score of 4.23, the respondents had a pretty strong formal education, indicating that the majority (96.6 percent) of dairy farmers were literate. Sixty-five percent of dairy farmers belonged to mixed families, while thirty-five percent belonged to nuclear families. The land holdings of the family varied from 1 to 6 acres, with an average of 2.60 acres. A herd of 3-5 dairy cows was favored by 43.3 percent of respondents. In general, respondents exhibited modest levels of social involvement, with a mean value of 0.16. Furthermore, with a mean score of 2.23, the majority of responders reported a low degree of extension contact. Dairy farmers' mass media exposure was equally low, with a mean score of 2.65, indicating that the majority (73.3 percent) of dairy farmers had little or no exposure to the media. However, dairy farmers' economic motivation was rather strong, with a mean score of 22.56. With a mean score of 18.28, dairy producers showed a medium risk orientation.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population's social, economic, health, and infrastructure aspects will be thoroughly examined in this research. The research is based on a field survey, secondary data, and data from GIS.

A. Data Collection method

The municipal committee of Hisar and the statistics department of Hisar provided information such as demographic figures for each ward, a ward-by-ward map of the study area, and a district gazetteer. Haryana Space Application Center (HARSAC) Hisar provided the digitized map of the research region and the information map (Hisar constituency). Explanatory data for the comparison of Hisar with Haryana and India came from the statistical abstract of Haryana and India, 2001, as well as tentative population numbers from the 2011 census of India. The research is based mostly on a field survey. The questionnaire includes information on social, economic, health, demographics, and infrastructure.

B. Sample

Because the study was done in rural locations, all of the data and variables utilized are specific to those areas and populations. The data from the 2011 Census were utilized to sample. Because religion-specific population data is only accessible up to the Tehsil level, stratification was limited to that level.

To begin, all of the districts' tehsils were grouped in decreasing order based on minority population. To put it another way, they were ordered such that the Tehsils with the largest number of minorities were at the top and the Tehsils with the lowest percentage of minorities were at the bottom. After that, the Tehsils were divided into three groups: the first group consists of the top 20% of Tehsils, organized by population; the second group consists of the middle 50%; and the third group consists of the remaining

30%. The PPS (Probability Proportionate to Size) approach was used to choose which communities to visit. The PPS approach was used to choose 30 villages from each of the three strata (25 villages were chosen in districts with a rural population of less than 5 lakh). The number of villages chosen from each stratum is determined by the ratio of the Tehsil's total population to the district's total population. For example, if the total population of all Tehsils in a strata is 20% of the total population, then 6 villages from that stratum have been chosen. It has also been assured that at least six communities from each stratum are chosen.

In all, 30 homes from each sample village were chosen for a comprehensive survey. These 30 households were picked in proportion to the total number of households mentioned in the respective frames from two selected hamlets (if hg's formed) and from among the corresponding SSS. A total of two homes were selected for the SSS. Stratified random sampling without replacement was used to choose the necessary number of sample houses from each SSS (SRSWOR). In villages with less than 30 homes, all of the households were polled.

C. HYPOTHESIS OF THE PRESENT STUDY

- H_0 Social and Economic development has a significant impact on individual's lifestyle.
- H_1 Social and Economic development has no impact on individual's lifestyle.

IV. RESULT AND FINDINGS

- Hisar district has a total population of 17,43, 531 people, with 68.26% of them living in rural regions. The scheduled castes (SCs) make up 26.65% of the population in India.
- Hindus are the most populous group in the poll (85.67%), followed by everyone else (14.33 per cent). The number of Muslims and Christians is insignificant. The average household size is 5.39 people, with Sikhs (5.33) having the smallest and Christians having the largest (6.70). Overall, reliance is high (1.44), with Sikhs (1.52) having the highest rate and Christians having the lowest rate (0.85).
- The average sex ratio is 824, which is quite high for Muslims (1027) and low for Christians (824). (603). When compared to Christians, Sikhs, and Hindus, Muslims have a higher sex ratio, which suggests a comparably superior female standing in the society, which may be related to greater educational level and women's empowerment.
- One-fifth of the population is between the ages of 15 and 24. Christian females have a higher (30.43%) presence in this age group than Christian men, who have a lower representation (10.34 per cent). Given the greater frequency of general unemployment and the present economic downturn, this means that other areas provided more male labor force, and that unemployment is likely higher in these towns.
- Nearly ten percent of the population is over 60 years old. Except for Muslims, gender inequality is low in this age range. • More Muslim males live to reach 60 years old, whereas none of the women in the sample homes live to be 60 years old. More over half of the households in the sample are landless. When compared to Hindus, Muslims

(78.80%) and Buddhists (59.10) are more likely to be landless (19.24 per cent). Landlessness is more common among Muslims (0.1%) and Christians (96.95%) than among Sikhs (42.94%) and Hindus (73.39%). In comparison to Hindu and Christian families, Sikh households have larger average landholdings. As a result, landlessness and the modest number of landholdings held by sample families limit their livelihood alternatives while also making them susceptible to low-wage jobs, trapping landless households in poverty.

- Christians (Rs. 3216), Muslims (Rs. 20081), Hindus (Rs. 19205), and Sikhs (Rs. 19205) all had lower per capita livestock values than Muslims (Rs. 20081), Hindus (Rs. 19205), and Sikhs (Rs. 19205). (Rs. 35315). Given the reduced value of cattle, the overall quality of animals owned by Christian families seems to be poor.

V. CONCLUSION

- Rural families now have more livestock, which provides them with draught power, milk animals, meat, and other goods, depending on the sorts of livestock they own and keep. Thus, cattle and dairy development programs must be increased in order to improve their livelihood circumstances, including nutritional requirements.
- Low female labor participation is a severe problem that needs proper governmental actions to increase their economic contribution and enable them to play an effective role both inside and outside the home.
- The government can improve the economic status of families by providing more fundamental health and educational services. This would lessen their reliance on private services, which depleted a portion of their income that might be used to satisfy other family requirements.
- Rural poor families' reliance on private sources of drinking water has to be addressed. The government should provide tap water facilities, with priority given to making the appropriate appropriations.
- Unemployment and underemployment are a major concern in many areas. Because the need for extra work to supplement family income and status is so great, their employability is comparably low due to a lack of training and skills. As a result, short-term vocational and job-oriented training are required to develop their skills.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Bishnoi, S., (2000), "Rural Settlements Analysis of Village SadalPur, District Hisar," Un-published M.Phil Dissertation, Department of Geography, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.
- [2.] Chen, L.C. and A.K., (2007), "Turnaround in China's Health Policies?" Indian Journal of Human Development, Vol. I, No. 1, pp. 163-165.
- [3.] Gayatri, K., (2004), "Urban Poverty- Issues ,Policies and Action," In Urban Poverty in India edited by Sandhu, R.S., Uppal Publishing House, New Delhi, pp. 53,54.
- [4.] Kaushik, S.P., (2001), "Spatial and Structural Pattern of Urban Population and Its Social and Economic Attributes in Haryana", Indian Journal of Geography and Environment, Vol. 8 and 9 : 2003-2004,

VidyaSagar University ,Medinipur West Bengal ,
India, pp. 52-63.

- [5.] Premi, M.K., (2006), “Social Demography: A Systematic Exposition,” Jawahar Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
- [6.] Rajeev and Dr. Satya Prakash Kaushik. “Social Well-Being and Economic Development of HisarCity , 2010.” (2015).
- [7.] Sain, Veer &Luhach, V.P. &Luhach, V.J. &Sindhu, S. &Mehla, M.S.. (2014). Economic analysis of guava production in Hisar district of Haryana state. 19. 340-342.
- [8.] *Rajpal*, 2016. Socio-Economic Status of Scheduled Castes in Hisar District of Haryana State. [online] 7(2), p.12. Available at: <<https://skirec.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/IJBEMR1Feb16-RRaj-2.pdf>> [Accessed 14 January 2022]
- [9.] Singh, Rachna. (2021). Socio-economic profile of dairy farmers in Hisar district of Haryana. THE ASIAN JOURNAL OF ANIMAL SCIENCE. 12. 88.